

EMERGENCE OF SINGLE PARENTHOOD IN NIGERIA AND ITS IMPLICATION TO CHILD REARING

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ABSTRACT

In Nigeria the existence of single parents is formerly unknown and where they existed, they are ignored as exceptional cases. However, nowadays, they are fast growing family pattern both inside and outside Nigeria. The paper explored the issue of single parenthood and its implication to child rearing and health education. Different types of single parent families have been named, factors that differentiate them advanced. The paper also mentioned various causes of single parenthood as well as problems associated with the situation. It examined various opinions on the outcome of single parenthood on the children and such families generally. Recommendation offered and directed toward the children in such families as well as their parents. It was also recommended that health education should be tailored towards the different type and causes of single parenthood.

KEYWORDS: parents, mother's contribution, child rearing, health education, social phenomenon, global dimension

INTRODUCTION

Single parenthood is a social phenomenon that has always been in existence and is as old as mankind. According to Pollitt (1994), single parent family is a household in which only one parent lives with a child or children. Single parenthood as viewed by Achakpa (1999) is the taking of family responsibility (which includes caring for children) without the father's or mother's contribution. Recently, the numbers of single parents' families have increased drastically and it is gaining a global dimension. This wind of change has also affected the Nigerian society where the idea of single parenthood seems to be a norm, rather than an anomaly, and children born to such families are legitimized if there had ever been a father in the scene or neglected. According to Pollitt (1994), the percentage of white women with some level of education who have become mothers without marrying has more than doubled in the last decade. Among women with professional or managerial jobs, it has almost tripled. The suggestion therefore is that, may be, marriage no longer serves women interest. If women can support themselves, they do not need to marry. They feel they are secured economically. If single a parent can have sex at will with any man she fancies, have her own house and gain the respect of friends and co-worker, she does not see any need to tie herself to the apron-string of any man in a bondage call marriage. Despite the prevalence and popularity of marriage, a significant proportion of adults in Nigerian society are unmarried. According to Linsel and Roth (1998), about 88 million American were single. In Nigeria there is dearth of information on the status of single parenthood.

Kibel and Wagstaff (2006) affirmed that the prevalence of single parenting is increasing and the pool is a composite of unmarried mothers (including many teenagers), divorcee and families separated by migrant labour arrangement. Single parenthood is seen as a deviant form of the normal family.

Family

The family according to Young Wolkowitz and McCullagh (1991) is an institution of principal importance in socialist society and is a primary target of reforming legislation. In official statements, it is conventionally referred to as the basic cell of society and functions as an agent of socialization. It is the main focus of the day-to-day responsibility for the welfare of children and the elderly. Therefore, the first approved step to starting a family is marriage, a secular contract which gives the couple's signatories equal rights within marriage and equal rights to divorce and to commonly owned property. Otite and Ogonwo (1998) stated that family is a vital unit in social organization and social control, and an important institution in many respects. It has also been described as a vital unit of social organization and social control.

Type of Single Parenthood

There are different types of single parenthood. Burge (1997) observed that the vast majority of single parent families are low income families consisting of a mother and her young children and are characterized by a high percentage of minority representation and relatively little formal education. Burge (1997) has also identified three major sub groups of one-parent families. These are displaced home markers (Divorced), adolescent mothers and single fathers. There are two main routes of entry into single parenthood. These include relationship breakdown and birth of a child outside marriage.

Differentiating factors among single parents

1. Marital status

One important criterion of differentiation between a male and female headed house hold is marital status (Kamerman and Khan, 1999).

2. Class

Class is clearly another important consideration. A higher socio economic status is likely to equip women with greater capacity, at least financially, to raise children alone or live independently. Also, a higher socio class position may make this more difficult in social terms. This reason clearly points to why some Nigerian ladies indulge in single parenthood, especially during Obasanjo's living wage era.

3. Race

The analysis of differences in lone parents on grounds of race has been subjected to greater investigation especially in respect to minority groups in advanced economics. This is partly because single parent may be more common among ethnic minority groups than in the vast population. For example in United States of America, 56.7% of all black families with children were headed by women compared with only 17.8% among white (Kamerman and Khan, 1999).

Causes of Single Parenthood

Various reasons have been adduced as to why people get into single parenthood. An early age at first marriage is associated with a higher probability of divorce and separation (Single and Samara, 1996). It has also been revealed that several factors contribute to the growing number of single parents. Among these is the changing view of single-hood, which is increasingly being viewed as a legitimate alternative to marriage. High divorce rate means more singles and people who have experienced divorce in their families may have more negative attitude about marriage and more positive attitude about single-hood.

The reasons commonly given by women for leaving her partner usually include: adultery, cruelty, desertion, addition to alcohol or drugs and husband imprisonment and the death of husband.

Problems Associated with Single Parenthood

Several problems have been known to be associated with Single parenthood. It has been pointed out that in addition to having fewer financial resources, single parent may be less able to supervise her adolescent children. There is evidence that an adolescent in a single parent family is susceptible to delinquent behavior and substance abuse as the situation is not conducive to successful child rearing. It has been observed that 55% of children living in female-headed families are poor and are five times poorer than children in other families.

Unmarried fathers are also not without problems and generally receive more condemnation than help. Generally, they have more healthy economic status than their female counterparts. Single fathers are often confronted with serious career related problems as they find their sole children rearing role conflicting with work expectation. Myles (2004) emphasized that stress is inherent in the situation of the woman trying to bring up her children alone. A husband may do little, but that little helps, and it is a comfort to have someone with whom to discuss the problem that may arise concerning the health, school performance and other matters concerning the offspring. Insecurity, financial pressure, lack of companion in the home and the burden of bringing up children alone; all constitute stressful conditions which take their toll on the health of women who find themselves in the situation of being single parents. Single-parenthood has to do with loneliness, hence many single parents find themselves feeling isolated at one point or another. It was reported that single parents who get pregnant are not allowed the benefit of maternity leave simply because they are not married. But the Beijing conference of 1996 has solved this problem.

Single parents commonly experience difficulty with role identity. Some form of social stigma is still attached to single-parent status regardless of how it was acquired. Many single parents are confused as to when a significant other should be introduced to their child/children. While it is never good to hide a growing relationship from the child, caution should be taken that the children don't become emotionally involved with someone her mother is dating unless the relationship is going to end in marriage.

IMPLICATION TO CHILD REARING

Hamburg (2004) opined that marital separation commonly involves major emotional distress for child relationship. Single parents try, as they will, tend to diminish parenting for several years after the break up. Hamburg (2004) observed that children aged six to eight (6-8) react with grief, fear and intense longing for reconciliation. Those aged nine to twelve (9-12 years) tend to be openly angry. They are inclined to reject a step parent. At both age groups, the children's behaviour at home and school often deteriorates. Bad companies and the existence of drug, rebelling, idleness, and marginalization are some of the fears and concerns that distress these mothers on their own.

Kibep and Wagstaff (2006) went on to suggest that social contacts by the single parent with members of the opposite sex may be a catalyst for unacceptable behaviour. The child perceive the mother's friend as an interloper who attracts attention seeking behaviour and even to aggressive act directed at the visitor. Malanahan and Saudeur (1999) found that about twice as many children from one parent families compare to two parents families drop out of high school. Very high rates of poverty have also been discovered among single parent families (Odumosu 1997). Lye *et al* (1990) concluded that children who spend part of their childhood in a step family, either because they were born to an unmarried mother or because their parents divorces, report significantly lower quality relationships with their parents as adults and have less frequent contact with them. Levitin (1999) also observed that a child from a single parent family in some cases became delinquent, failing in school, developing inappropriate sex role attitudes and behaviours, or exhibiting other types of pathology. Teachers commonly describe children from single parents as more hostile, aggressive, anxious, fearful, hyperactive and distractible than children from intact families (Nwachukwu, 2006).

Recommendation and the role of health education in control of simple parenthood

For the purpose of this paper, emotional well-being is a necessity for a holistic health status. Health education should be tailored towards the different types and causes of single parenthood among which are teenage pregnancy, married but separated or divorced and never married parents. Health education in the case of teenage pregnancy should concentrate on reproductive health with move emphasis on family planning and abstinence from sexual intercourse among adolescents.

Divorced parents should be made to see the need for reunion and stability for companionship and for children upbringing. Religious group should be made to take active role in this regard. The government too should formulate policy on the care of children coming from single parent. This will drastically reduce crime rate in Nigerian society.

CONCLUSION

Simple parenthood is a very sensitive issue in Nigeria. The paper has attempts a discussion on some of the type of simple parenthood that exists as well as some of the reasons why people become single parents.

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